

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE *DIAEA* SPECIES OF SOUTH AFRICA

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DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. (2020). The Thomisidae of South Africa (A-Mo). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: Part 1 Version 1: 1-62. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513274>

1. *Diaea albicincta* Pavesi, 1883

2. *Diaea longisetosa* Roewer, 1961

3. *Diaea puncta* Karsch, 1884

4. *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923

5. *Diaea viridipes* Strand, 1909

